

A Middle Assyrian Juridical Text on a Tablet with Handle*

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1. Introduction

In this paper, we aim to review the text of a Middle Assyrian cuneiform tablet with a perforated handle. In all probability, it records an inheritance to be shared between siblings, as indicated on the small amulet shaped or moulded tablet, which we prefer to designate in this article as a tablet with handle. This will be further discussed below. First, we will transliterate, translate and philologically comment on the text on the tablet. We will then analyse the possible function of the inscribed tablet in comparison with similar tablets of the same format. We will also discuss further evidence of administrative texts written on tablets with handle, which were displayed and made visible in domestic contexts.

BM 103395 is a small tablet and most likely originates from the city of Ashur. This item is held nowadays in the British Museum. The artefact was probably smuggled out by a worker during the German excavations in Ashur at the beginning of the twentieth century and then taken to the British Museum.¹ As a result, the tablet's text was published in 1912 by Leonard W. King in *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets from the British Museum*, part 33, pl. 15. To date, despite some notes, the text has not been translated, transliterated or been the subject of critical comment.² The text probably describes an arrangement between three brothers and a sister as to the distribution of objects belonging to their inheritance.

* The authors would like to thank the Trustees of the British Museum and Jonathan Taylor for allowing Strahil Panayotov to study the tablet and publish photographs of the artefact. Furthermore, we thank Joachim Marzahn for permission to study VAT 9032 in the *Vorderasiatisches Museum* Berlin, David Kertai for comments on an earlier draft and Steven Patten for English corrections. Jaume Llop would like to express thanks for the funding provided by the Gerda Henkel foundation and the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (project FFI2011-25290).

¹ The provenance of BM 103395 was discussed by Ernst Weidner in, "Amts- und Privatarchive aus Mittelassyrischer Zeit," 118 note 26. See also the description by Leonard King, *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets, &c., in the British Museum Part 33*, 6.

² The tablet was mentioned by Stefan Jakob, *Mittelassyrische Verwaltung und Sozialstruktur*, 235 among the attestations for *tupšarru* "scribe" in the Middle Assyrian period.

2. Transliteration

BM 103395 = ca. 5.3 x 4.5 x 1.5 cm. See copy and photographs on Table 1 pp. 10–11.

Obv. 1	^{m.d} 30- <i>ni-ya</i>	
2	^ṛ munus ^ṛ <i>Di-li-li-ya</i>	
3	^m Ma ²¹ - <i>nu-bal</i> - ^d IŠKUR	
4	^m AN ^{nu} - <i>ma-lik</i>	
<hr/>		
5	BAD ^ṛ X X (X) I ² X <i>an-na-ti</i>	
6	^ṛ KU ² X ^ṛ [X X (X) X X]X	
7	Signs are badly broken.	
l.e.	[X X]X ^ṛ X ^ṛ ša ² [X X X]	
Rev. 1	[<i>a-n</i>]a ² ^ṛ zi ^ṛ - ^ṛ ti ^ṛ - ^ṛ šu ^ṛ - ^ṛ n[u]	
2	^ṛ li ^ṛ - <i>pu-šu</i>	
3	^{gi} BANŠUR*(URU.DUB).MEŠ	The rest of the line is left intentionally empty. Probably, this is because <i>an-na-ti</i> from the obv. 5 continues onto this line.
4	^m Ma-nu-bal- ^ṛ d ^ṛ IŠKUR <i>i-dan</i>	
	Lines 4 and 5 are separated by an empty space and thus accented.	
5	ⁱⁱⁱ d30 {LU} ^ṛ UD.21.KAM ^ṛ	
6	<i>li-mu</i> ^{m.d} MAR.TU- ^ṛ ma ^ṛ -DINGIR	
7	IGI ^m Šil-li-Ku-bé	Lines 7 and 8 are written on the handle.
8	<i>tup-šar-ṛ</i> ru ² ^ṛ	

3. Translation

obv. 1–4) *Sînīya*, *Dilīlīya*, *Mannu-bal-Adad* and *Anu-mālik*.

5) these ...

6–7) ...

r. 1–2) may they make for their (inheritance) share.

3–4) *Mannu-bal-Adad* will deliver the tables.

5–6) Month *Sîn*, 21st day, eponym *Amurrūma-ilī*.

7–8) Witness: *Šilli-Kube*, the scribe (?).

4. Commentary

Obv. 1–2) *Sînīya* and *Dilīlīya* are well known hypocoristic personal names from the Middle Assyrian period.³ The form of the sign LI is peculiar. This sign is written

³ For *Sînīya*, see Saporetti, *Onomastica*, 398; Helmut Freydank, and Claudio Saporetti, *Nuove Attestazioni Dell’Onomastica*, 108. For *Dilīlīya*, see Wolfram von Soden, *Akkadisches Handwörterbuch*, 154; A. Leo Oppenheim, and Erica Reiner, et al. (ed.), *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary* D, 50f.; Claudio Saporetti, *Onomastica medio-assira* I, 194.

in different ways on the obverse and on the reverse of the tablet. On the obverse of line 2 the sign is written at the beginning with ŠE, but not followed by three horizontal wedges. In contrast, on the reverse of lines 2 and 6, three horizontal wedges follow the sign ŠE. This clearly illustrates how a scribe can write the same sign with dissimilar shapes on the same tablet.

Obv. 3) The name ^mMa²-nu-BAL-^dŠKUR has been interpreted differently in Assyriological literature. On the one hand, Cl. Saporetti renders the name as *Mannu-gēr-Adad* “who is the enemy of Adad?”⁴ On the other hand, E. Weidner provides evidence that this name should be read as *Mannu-bal-Adad*.⁵ Later, this is agreed by Saporetti, H. Freydank, the *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary* and D. Schwemer as well.⁶ Therefore, we read *Mannu-bal-Adad* and understand the name as a rhetorical question “who can be (i.e., exist) without Adad?”

Obv. 4) The personal name Anu-mālik is attested in at least two other MA documents.⁷

Obv. 5) It is hard to tell what this badly damaged line originally contained. The first sign is probably BAD. Afterwards, in the damaged part, it is possible to restore the sign I, but this interpretation is far from certain. We cannot tell which word stood here originally, but at the end of the line we read the demonstrative pronoun *annāti*. This suggests that a plural feminine name or several feminine names once stood in the broken part. The space on this line is limited. Therefore, we propose that a plural feminine name should be reconstructed in the broken part of this line.

Obv. 6–7 and l.e.) The following lines are almost completely lost. It is conceivable that they possibly contained the names of additional objects, which would have been distributed among the persons named in the beginning of the tablet, obv. 1–4.

Rev. 1–2) The verb *epāšu* appears to be linked to the word *zittu* and the Hurrian loanword *šaššummu*. This can be seen in the expression *ina zittīšu ša abīšu šaššumma eppušu*. The meaning of this expression is “forfeiting someone’s share” and it appears in some Nuzi texts.⁸ The word *epāšu* is linked to *zittu* through a preposition, which, in this case, may be *ana*, if we take into account the small space at the beginning of the line. This preposition is partly reconstructed at the beginning of the line, hence the translation: “to make into/as their share.” This expression, if we follow the dictionaries, is not attested in Middle Assyrian. The subject of the precative form *līpušu* are the persons mentioned in lines obv. 1–4. The direct object (for accusative, see *annāti* on line obv. 5) of the verb *epāšu* could

⁴ Saporetti, *Onomastica*, 306.

⁵ Ernst Weidner, “Review of Saporetti, *Onomastica medio-assira* I,” 141b.

⁶ Freydank and Saporetti, *Nuove Attestazioni*, 81 and Oppenheim et al., *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary* B, 70f.; Daniel Schwemer, *Die Wettergottgestalten*, 586.

⁷ Von Soden, *Handwörterbuch*, 595 f.; Oppenheim et al., *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary* M/I, 164b; Saporetti, *Onomastica*, 88; Freydank and Saporetti, *Nuove Attestazioni*, 27.

⁸ Von Soden, *Handwörterbuch*, 1198b and Oppenheim et al., *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary* Z, 140b–141a, 8’.

be some of the objects listed in the badly preserved lines obv. 5 to 7 and the lower edge. The extensive damage renders the interpretation of the passage difficult. We suggest two possibilities for an understanding of these lines. On the one hand, it could be that the lines describe a work-contract between artisans to produce tables (see line r. 4). However, as far as we are aware, the substantive *zittu* is not attested in these types of document. Moreover, the presence of a woman, Dililīya, in obv. line 2 among the mentioned individuals makes it more likely that the lines describe an agreement between siblings, regarding some division of a conceivable inheritance. As far as we know, women are not attested as being among artisans producing tables (see below) in the Middle Assyrian period.⁹

Rev. 3–4) As far as we can tell, tables are attested twice as objects for distribution in Middle Assyrian testaments: 1 GIŠ.BANŠUR *ša na-ap-te-né qa-al-lu*, “one small dining table,” TR 2037: 36-37¹⁰ and 2 GIŠ.BANŠUR, “two tables,” *MARV* 8, 47: 15. The writing of BANŠUR, with the signs URU+DUB, often appears in Middle Assyrian (see, for example: *MARV* 2, 6 I 9, 28² and *passim* in this tablet; *MARV* 4, 89 III 7’.¹¹ On the contrary, the writing of BANŠUR with the signs URU+URUDU appears only once (*MARV* 9, 109: 2), in contrast to the Neo-Assyrian period, where URU+URUDU is very common.¹²

Rev. 5) The writing of the date on this tablet is unusual. It contains the name of the fourth month of the Assyrian calendar (see *MARV* 2, 19: 6). The month’s name is usually written with the signs ^(dingir)30, and more rarely syllabically *su-en*. The day (UD.n.KAM/KÁM) usually directly follows the month. But in BM 103395 the sign LU is written between the name of the month and the day (see also *CT* 33, 15b and the copy below). Such writing does not appear elsewhere. The sign LU seems clear from the collations, and has not been written over an erasure. Nevertheless, the sign is slightly smaller in comparison with the other signs on the same line. This sign is either a scribal error, or it is a type of notation that we do not understand.

Rev. 6) The eponym Amurrūma-ilī is placed by Saporetti in the reign of Aššur-uballiṭ I (1353–1318 B.C.).¹³ Therefore, we have a possible dating for this text in the 14th century B.C. Thus, if the dating of the artefact is correct, this tablet is one of the earliest known examples of such a tablet format and it seems to be the earliest of the Middle Assyrian period.

Rev. 7–8) A scribe by the name of Šilli-Kube is attested in *KAJ* 79 (= 166): 25. He is the son of Abī-ilī and is qualified as a *tupšar mumme* “scribe of the Mummy-house.”¹⁴ Another scribe with the same name was the son of Dugul-Šamaš, as the

⁹ See Jakob, *Verwaltung*, 449–52.

¹⁰ Henry Saggs, “Tell al Rimah Tablets,” pl. 47 and John N. Postgate, “On Some Assyrian Ladies,” 89–91. Oppenheim et al., *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary* P, 260b.

¹¹ See also Bahija K. Ismail & John N. Postgate, “A Middle Assyrian flock-master’s archive from Tell Ali,” 165, no. 11: 7.

¹² See, e.g., Rykle Borger, *Mesopotamisches Zeichenlexikon*, no. 75.

¹³ Saporetti, *Onomastica*, 85 and idem, *Eponimi*, 45.

¹⁴ Idem, *Onomastica*, 418.1.

documents *KAJ* 41: 21 and *KAJ* 34: 21 show.¹⁵ Both scribes seem to have been active during the reign of Aššur-uballit.¹⁶ The first scribe was in charge during the same year of Amurrūma-ilī as Šilli-Kube in BM 103395.¹⁷ Therefore, it is possible to connect the name of Šilli-Kube in *KAJ* 79 and in BM 103395, and we propose that this name belonged to the same person. The traces of the sign after DUB.SAR are not quite clear, because the sign is written over an erasure. The sign appears to be neither a DUMU (filiation is not present), nor a MU (see copy below). A reading *tup-šar-ri* seems plausible.¹⁸ Nevertheless, according to the traces under the sign AŠ (here with a syllabic value of *-ri*), Panayotov suggests that an erased DINGIR sign was written first. It seems that the scribe first intended to write *tupšar ili*, but then he erased the DINGIR and wrote AŠ above it. If we take into consideration that the *bīt mumme* was in the grounds of, or associated with the temple of the god Aššur,¹⁹ then the qualification, *tupšar ili*, would be metonymically appropriate in the case of the scribe Šilli-Kube.

5. Format of the artefact and its function

BM 103395 has a pierced handle. Therefore, we can state that it was meant to be hung up. Because of this and because of the same shape of such artefacts as with the shape of the Lamaštu amulets and plaques, this format is usually referred to as an amulet shaped, moulded tablet or *Amuletttafel*.²⁰ This kind of artefact contained magical and apotropaic texts. Common examples include rituals, Lamaštu incantations, Ḫulabazizi incantations, Namburbi incantations, tablets with the Erra epos and other incantations.²¹ They served as apotropaic objects, and may be described as types of amulet, which were usually hung in a domestic context and served as magical protective tools against demons, diseases, witchcraft, bad luck and similar calamities. On the other hand, there are tablets with this format that

¹⁵ Ibid., 418.2.

¹⁶ Idem, *Eponimi*, 45.

¹⁷ Idem, *Onomastica*, 419.10 cited as King, *Cuneiform Texts* 33, 15b.

¹⁸ King, *Cuneiform Texts* 33, 15b; followed by Jakob, *Verwaltung*, 235.

¹⁹ See Brigitte Menzel, *Assyrische Tempel* I, 287.

²⁰ For this designation, see for instance Pedersén *Archives and Libraries*, 75, 81. Nathan Wasserman, “A Neo-Babylonian Imposture Of An Old-Babylonian Amulet?,” 51–53. See also Joachim Marzahn, “Ein Amulett-Rohling aus Assur,” 41–46, Jacob Lauinger, “Some Preliminary Thoughts on the Tablet Collection in Building XVI from Tell Tayinat,” 10–11, and the works by Erica Reiner, Rita Strauß and Stefan Maul, which are cited in the next footnote.

²¹ For a provisional sketch of such texts, see Erica Reiner, “Plague Amulets and House Blessings,” 148–55. Recently, Stefan Maul, and Rita Strauß, *Ritualbeschreibungen und Gebete*, 3, no. 22 and 23, and a list of these tablets from Aššur, 4 note 25. For a classification of the Lamaštu amulets, see Frans A. M. Wiggermann, “Lamaštu, daughter of Anu. A Profile,” 217–49, with an addition in Frans A. M. Wiggermann, “Dogs, Pigs, Lamaštu, and Breast-Feeding of Animals by Women,” 407 note 4.

do not contain apotropaic texts and do not have such an apotropaic function at all. Therefore, it is better not to describe them as amulets. Moreover, most of the small amulets, as stone, cylinder or stamp seals etc., do not have the shape of this specific tablet format. Because of these reasons, it is proposed that another term should be used. To avoid a magical connotation and to describe the essence of the format, such an artefact is better referred to as a tablet with handle rather than as an amulet shaped or moulded tablet.

The materiality of the artefact shows the following features: the specific format has eight angles and not four edges, as is the case with common tablets. It consists of two major parts – the body, the larger section with the handle, and the smaller one. The body of BM 103395 has a handle on the top. It was modelled together with the tablet's body and was additionally pierced, thus allowing the tablet to be hung up with a string or a wire. Traces of it are still visible around the two sides of the bore hole. Furthermore, lines were ruled after obv. line 4. Consequently, the tablet was inscribed and then dried – this particular type of tablet was not baked in antiquity. On the front side of the tablet, a sheet of clay appears to be visible, which may suggest that it was manufactured by wrapping clay around a core, or folding a clay sheet.²² It can be dated to the reign of Aššur-uballiṭ I (1353–1318 B.C.; see com. rev. 6). It is the earliest example published so far of a tablet with handle from the Middle Assyrian period. From this period, two more tablets are known that have an administrative context.

A further administrative item from Ashur is located in Berlin, VAT 9032²³ (ca. 4.9 x 3.9 cm), and it remains to be published. Its size is very similar to BM 103395. The form of the signs and the contents of the tablet (e.g., personal names, see below) indicate that it was written in the Middle Assyrian period. The handle of the tablet is pierced as well, thus allowing the artefact to be hung up. The text on it mentions the following persons: [M]ušallim-Aššur and Bābu-aḥa-iddina (obv. 2 [(x) ^(m)m]u-šal-lim-^dA-šur^r obv. 3 [ina^a a²-b]at^m KÁ-A-PAP²⁴). A person with the name *Mušallim-Aššur* functioned as a representative of *Bābu-aḥa-iddina*.²⁵ A person with this name is the famous high official of *Shalmaneser* I.²⁶ Therefore,

²² For different methods of manufacturing a cuneiform tablet see the description in Jonathan Taylor, “Tablets as artefacts, scribes as artisans,” 7ff. and Jonathan Taylor, and Caroline Cartwright, “The Making and Re-Making of Clay Tablets,” 297–320.

²³ Reference, courtesy of Stefan Jakob.

²⁴ Here ^mKÁ-A-PAP should not be read *Bābu-apla-ušur* but *Bābu-aḥa-iddina*, see Olof Pedersén *Archives and Libraries in the City of Assur* I, 107 note 5, and Olof Pedersén, “A Problematic King in the Assyrian King List,” 372.

²⁵ Apart from the eponym of *Shalmaneser* I, dating at least one of the tablets from M 11 (RIAA 311), the personal name *Mušallim-Aššur* often appears in the tablets of this archive, designating one of the representatives (*qēpu*, pl. *qēpūtu*) of *Bābu-aḥa-iddina*, see attestations in Claudio Saporetti, *Onomastica medio-assira* I, 333 sub 6. See also Stefan Jakob, *Verwaltung*, 264. See also Donbaz, “Bābu-aḥa-iddina’s archive in Istanbul,” 101–109.

²⁶ For attestations of this personal name, see Claudio Saporetti, *Onomastica medio-assira* I, 154–56 and Freydank and Saporetti, *Nuove Attestazioni*, 41. See also Stefan Jakob, *Verwaltung*, 58.

VAT 9032 can be most likely dated to the reign of *Shalmaneser* I (1263–1234 B.C.). If this dating is correct, then this object must have belonged to the archive of Ashur M 11.²⁷

A further artefact, which most probably belongs to an administrative context, is a blank tablet, also stored in Berlin, VAT 15568 (ca. 8.1 x 6.1 x 2.2 cm). Although the tablet is blank, which is very unusual to find,²⁸ it is probably associated with the above-mentioned texts. It was prepared to contain an inscription; ruled lines were drawn, but afterwards left blank for unknown reasons. In contrast to the tablets above, its handle was not pierced. The artefact most probably dates to the Middle Assyrian period and was found in an administrative context, together with the other documents of the archive of Ashur M 7.²⁹ This is also the only *tertium comparationis* to the above-mentioned texts. The contexts in which the above-mentioned tablets were found suggest that the presence of tablets with handle within an administrative archive is less unusual than currently believed.³⁰

The administrative contents of tablets BM 103395 and VAT 9032 do not suggest any apotropaic or magical function or connotation. Rather, its design seems to have been chosen in order to allow the texts to be displayed³¹ in an analogous way. By hanging up the tablet with its text, a visual record was provided on the way in which the brothers and sister shared the inherited tables (rev. 3f.). Tables were mentioned in divisions of inheritance, because in Mesopotamian households, tables were likely to have been made of wood and were, therefore, very valuable.³²

As the archaeological context of BM 103395 is unknown, we cannot answer the question as to its original place of display by hanging. One may assume that the object would have been hung in the house containing the tables which were to be shared among the heirs of the family. On the other hand, the tablet with handle could also have functioned as a label, by hanging it on one of the mentioned tables,

²⁷ See Olof Pedersén, *Archives and Libraries*, 106–12.

²⁸ Jonathan Taylor, “Tablets as artefacts,” 8.

²⁹ Olof Pedersén *Archives and Libraries*, 75, 81 (237).

³⁰ Joachim Marzahn, who published VAT 15568 as “Einzeldenkmal,” questioned why such a tablet was found in the context of an administrative archive: “Die sich aus einem solchen Fundkontext ergebende spontane Frage, was ein Amulett unter Verwaltungsurkunden zu suchen hat, lässt sich leider vorerst nicht beantworten.” Marzahn, “Ein Amulett-Rohling aus Assur,” 44. The answer to his question is probably that this tablet was not an amulet.

³¹ The term “displayed” for tablets with handle, inscribed with hemerologies, was used by Jacob Lauinger, “Some Preliminary Thoughts on the Tablet Collection in Building XVI from Tell Tayinat,” 5–12. It seems that he considers the hemerologies with *iqqur ipuš* as amulets, although they do not have an apotropaic function.

³² See commentary to rev. 3–4. Further, see Oppenheim et al., *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary* P, 260ff. and Armas Salonen, *Die Möbel des Alten Mesopotamien*, 174ff. and 213ff. For the Old Babylonian period see Marten Stol, “Wirtschaft und Gesellschaft in Altbabylonischer Zeit,” 690, 710 and Gábor Kalla, “Nachlaß. B. Altbabylonisch,” 38, 41. The case of the doors is similar, see Claus Ambos, *Tür und Tor*, forthcoming in *Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie*.

pointing more directly to the shared object. We will exclude the last probability because the unbaked tablet is fragile and could easily have been destroyed in such a case. In both instances the tablet would have functioned as a visual label testifying to the division of the inheritance. By displaying the tablet with this administrative text on it, the distribution of the tables was made visible and permanent in a supposed domestic context. Therefore, in case of any doubt, one could have directly and easily consulted the hanging tablet, which would have provided proof of the eventual ownership of the tables.³³ Lastly, although one might speculate that the presence of such objects fostered magical connotations for the Assyrians, this cannot presently be substantiated. Nevertheless, these tablets show one way in which it was possible to write administrative texts on tablets with handles in order to display and make visible the object and its content in the Middle Assyrian period.

Abbreviations

The bibliographical abbreviations used in this article can be found in M. P. Streck (ed.), *Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatische Archäologie*, available at <http://www.rla.badw.de/>.

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³³ In cases where the person consulting the artefact could read.

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Table 1

(Copy S. V. Panayotov)

